

REDCap Training

GW4

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Preface

This information was written November 2023 and is based on REDCap version v13.7.X.

This document is aimed at users with View & Edit permissions. You may find some of the options described in this document may not be available to you, depending on your assigned user rights. Please contact your Project's administrator if you think you need your user rights amending.

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1. How to Navigate Your Project

1.1 How To Login Into Redcap

On the first screen complete the Username and Password provided by the admin of your system.

The screenshot shows the REDCap login interface. At the top left is the REDCap logo. To the right, a pink bar contains the text "BTC Test System". Below the logo is the text "Log In" and "BTC Test system" in a larger, bold font. A horizontal line separates the header from the main content. Below the line, there is a paragraph of text: "Please log in with your user name and password. If you are having trouble logging in, please contact [REDCap Administrator](#)." Below this text are two input fields: "Username:" and "Password:". The "Password:" field is masked with dots. Below the input fields are two buttons: "Log In" and "Forgot your password?".

1.2 Password Recovery

If you have forgotten your password, you can recover it by clicking on the **"Forgot your password"** link. It will take you to a **"REDCap Password Recovery"** and after entering your username it will send your password reset link via email.

REDCap Password Recovery

You may use this page to reset your REDCap password. You must first provide your REDCap username, and if it is an authentic REDCap account, an email containing a link for resetting your password will be sent to the primary email address associated with your REDCap account, after which you will then be able log in to your account.

The screenshot shows the REDCap Password Recovery form. It has a light blue background. On the left, the text "Username:" is displayed. To the right of this text is a white input field. Below the input field is a blue button with a white envelope icon and the text "Send password reset email".

1.3 How to Access and Organise Your Projects

Click on "My projects" on the top menu.

A list of projects which you have been granted access to will be displayed. To access a project, click on the project name and this will take you into the project details.

BTC Test system

Listed below are the REDCap projects to which you currently have access. Click the project title to open the project. [Read more](#) To review which users still have access to your projects, visit the [User Access Dashboard](#).

Project Title	Records	Fields	Instruments	Type	Status
GW4 - Training Project (Medium)	2	11	2 surveys		
GW4 - Training Project (Basic)	3	44	5 forms 1 survey		
TEST 123 Project	0	2	1 form		
ABC TEST Project	0	2	1 form		
XYZ TEST Project	0	2	1 form		

The list of projects can be organised in folders for easier accessibility. To do this click on **Organise**.

Enter the folder title, click "Add".

Projects can be organized into folders. Folder titles and background colours can be customised to enhance organization. Users can also personalize the folder appearance by selecting their preferred background and font colours.

The list of projects will be featured organised by folders. The + button can be used to expand or collapse the folders.

BTC Test system

Listed below are the REDCap projects to which you currently have access. Click the project title to open the project. [Read more](#) To review which users still have access to your projects, visit the [User Access Dashboard](#).

Project Title	Records	Fields	Instruments	Type	Status
My Projects Organize Collapse All <input type="text" value="Filter projects by title"/>					
Live projects (2)					
GW4 - Training Project (Medium)	2	11	2 surveys		
GW4 - Training Project (Basic)	3	45	5 forms, 1 survey		
Training projects (3)					
TEST 123 Project	0	2	1 form		
ABC TEST Project	0	2	1 form		
XYZ TEST Project	0	2	1 form		

2. Left-Hand Navigation Menu

REDCap features can be accessed via the left-hand navigation bar. This section provides a summary of each of the following:

2.1 Top Section

2.2 Project Home and Design

2.3 Data Collection

2.4 Applications

2.5 Help and Information

2.1 Top Section

The first section allows users to navigate between projects ("My Projects") (see section 1), check any notifications via "REDCap Messenger", and to report any technical concerns or difficulties via "Contact REDCap administrator". The user can also **log out** of REDCap from this section.

2.2 Project Home and Design

When first entering a project from the "My Projects" page, the user will automatically enter the "Project Home" page. This page displays the "Current users" (people who have access to the project), the "Project Statistics" which shows information such as the total number of records in the project, and any "Upcoming Calendar Events" in the next 7 days. The picture below shows an example of this page:

[Project Home](#)

The tables below provide general dashboard information, such as a list of all users with access to this project, general project statistics, and upcoming calendar events (if any).

Current Users (13)	
User	Expires

Project Statistics	
Records in project	4
Most recent activity	12-10-2023 13:05
Space usage for docs	1.13 MB

Upcoming Calendar Events (next 7 days)		
Time	Date	Description
		No upcoming events

The “Codebook” gives users a reference to view the field names, labels and attributes; it is a read-only version of the data dictionary.

2.3 Data Collection

Data Collection

- Record Status Dashboard**
- View data collection status of all records
- Add / Edit Records**
- Create new records or edit/view existing ones

The “Data Collection” section allows users to view the “Record Status Dashboard”, where users can view participant records on the study. To view all records and update a form, the Record Status Dashboard will allow choice between Record IDs and allow the users to view completion status of all the CRFs.

The “Add/Edit Records” is used to: to add a new record click on the green “+Add new record”, as shown below. Or, to update an existing participants record, click on the “—select record —” drop-down, and choose the relevant form to complete.

Total records: 4

Choose an existing Record ID	-- select record -- ▾
+ Add new record	

For data entry on the fields on an Instrument (used interchangeably with data collection form/CRF, please go to Section 4.

2.4 Applications

The applications available to users include the **Calendar**, **Data Exports, Reports, and Stats**, as well as a **Field Comment Log** and **File Repository**.

The **Calendar** section allows users to keep track of dates for events (explained in more detail in section 13). Data can be exported by choosing the relevant report under the **Data Exports, Reports, And Stats** section. Users can leave comments on any fields by using the **Field Comment Log**, for example by responding to queries. The **File Repository** can be used to store and organise files within the project, as well as share them with other users.

2.5 Help and Information

This final section of the navigation panel allows users to find relevant information regarding using REDCap Academic, either by reading through the **Help & FAQ** section, or watching the **Video Tutorials**.

3. Record Status Dashboard

Below is a screenshot of a 'Record Status Dashboard', which is something that you will find in every REDCap project:

Record Status Dashboard (all records)

Displayed below is a table listing all existing records/responses and their status for every data collection instrument (and if longitudinal, for every event). You may click any of the colored buttons in the table to open a new tab/window in your browser to view that record on that particular data collection instrument. Please note that if your form-level user privileges are restricted for certain data collection instruments, you will only be able to view those instruments, and if you belong to a Data Access Group, you will only be able to view records that belong to your group.

Legend for status icons:

- Incomplete Incomplete (no data saved) ?
- Unverified Partial Survey Response
- Complete Completed Survey Response

Dashboard displayed: [Default dashboard] ▼

Displaying Data Access Group -- ALL -- ▼

Displaying record Page 1 of 1: "1" through "824-1" ▼ of **4** records ALL (4) ▼ records per page

+ Add new record

Displaying: [Instrument status only](#) | [Lock status only](#) | [All status types](#)

Record ID	Screening						Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
	Patient Details	Screening Log	Randomisation	Questionnaire	Withdrawal	Note to File	Treatment	Treatment	Treatment
1	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
824-1	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3.1 Adding New Records

Depending on how the REDCap project has been setup, there are several ways that new records can be added to a project:

Method 1: '+ Add new record' Button

This is a very standard setup where records are automatically assigned consecutive Record IDs starting from '1'. The next record will be automatically assigned the Record ID '2' etc, etc. In this circumstance the method for creating will be a green button that says '+ Add new record'.

+ Add new record

Method 2: '+ Create' Button

This is another very standard setup, where the user enters a Record ID manually in the field provided and then clicks the '+ Create' button.

Enter new record name for this arm + Create

With methods 1 and 2 it can be only one of the other. You cannot have both these methods on a project.

Once you have clicked on the '+ Add new record', or '+ Create' button you will be taken to the record Home Page for the record. The data collection forms are known on REDCap as Instruments. To complete the forms, click on the circle for the respective instrument and timepoint. If 'Form Display Logic' has been used on the project to specify an order of what instruments must be completed first (to stop users doing things in the wrong order) then some of the instruments will be greyed out (inactive) and you will not be able to open them. They will activate once the pre-requisite forms have been completed or required branching logic (for example eligibility) being met.

Record Home Page

Record "4" is a new Record ID. To create the record and begin entering data for it, click any gray status icon below.

The grid below displays the form-by-form progress of data entered for the currently selected record. You may click on the colored status icons to access that form/event.

Legend for status icons:

- Incomplete ? Incomplete (no data saved)
- Unverified ● Partial Survey Response
- Complete ✔ Completed Survey Response

NEW Record ID 4

Data Collection Instrument	Screening	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Patient Details (survey)	●			
Screening Log	●			
Randomisation	●			
Treatment		●	●	●
Questionnaire (survey)	●			
Withdrawal	●			
Note to File	●			

Method 3: Public Survey Link

Records can be created by participants completing a public survey. This only works if the respective survey instrument is the first instrument in the project. Here is a link to a survey which will create a record in our 'GW4 - Training Project (Basic)' project:

<https://btc-test.bristol.ac.uk/redcap/surveys/?s=48Mnk9DDARA3RKFC>.

Please click on the link above to complete the survey, which will in turn create a record in our project.

This is a screenshot of the survey as an example of a REDCap survey:

Patient Details AAA
⊕ ⊞

Study ID:
* must provide value

First name:
* must provide value

Last name:
* must provide value

Method 4: Data Import

Records can also be created in a project using a data import using a CSV file.

Method 5: External Data Entry Trigger

Records can also be created in a project by an external trigger when something else happens outside of the project.

3.2 Custom Dashboards

The Record Status Dashboard by default displays the 'Default dashboard', but it is possible for Administrators to create additional dashboards (for other REDCap users to use) and these will be available under the 'Dashboard displayed' dropdown menu:

Custom dashboards are very useful if you have:

- a lot of instruments and/or events in your project and you just want to show either a particular stage in the participant pathway,
- instruments that are specific to certain roles.
- to do specific tasks when another task has been completed: filtering can be used to show records that meet certain criteria

In a custom dashboard the records can also be sorted by something other than Record ID and it is possible to orientate the instrument names vertically; this can help to squeeze more on a page when you have a lot of instruments and/or events.

When a user selects a custom dashboard, REDCap will default to the custom dashboard every time they visit the project. If they want to use the default dashboard again, they will need select this. REDCap will always remember the dashboard that the user last used.

3.3 Form Display Logic

As mentioned above, it is possible to have instruments that users cannot open at all until certain criteria have been met. An example of how this would be useful would be for example keeping the randomisation instrument inaccessible until a valid consent has been entered. In the small screenshot below you can see two status icons:

The first is an instrument that currently has no data (as it's grey), but it can be accessed.

The second also has no data (as it's grey), but cannot be opened yet. This means that some criteria in the Form Display Logic has not yet been met.

3.4 Repeating Instruments and Repeating Events

Within a REDCap project instruments or events can be enabled by an Administrator to repeat as required.

An example of where it might be useful to have a repeating instrument is for a 'Note to File' instrument that can be completed multiple times ad-hoc throughout the trial.

An example of where it might be useful to have a repeating event is for safety reporting, where 2 or more related and associated forms need to be completed, the first form is often the details of the event, and the other related forms are follow-up information about that event. By using a repeating event in this scenario, we can keep forms that relate to one event together and additional events can be completed as required.

Withdrawal	Note to File

When an instrument is a repeating instrument, you can see this in the dashboard, because the status icons are aligned to the left for this instrument. In the screenshot below you can see that the 'Note to File' instrument is a repeating one, whereas the 'Withdrawal' one is not.

Once the first instance of a repeating instrument has been completed you will see a '+' next to it.

Next time a 'Note to File' needs to be completed for this record, the REDCap user will need to click on the '+' to create another instance of this instrument, after which the status icon will look different to show that there has been more than one instance:

When you have repeating instruments in a project, these will appear in the Record Home Page for any record where they have been completed:

Repeating events work in much the same way, but naturally the whole event repeats. You cannot create a new instance of a repeating event from the Record Status Dashboard. In order to do this, you must open the Record Home Page for the record in question. Once the first instance of a repeating event has been completed, you can create the next instance by clicking on the '+ Add new' button in the event row on the first instance.

4. Using Data Collection Instruments

4.1 How to Enter Data

Each form in REDCap is referred to as an Instrument. This is where trial data is entered. To enter data, click onto an instrument and then data can be entered into the fields. 'Tab' can be used to move between data entry fields.

To change entered data, go back to the field, change the data and enter a Reason for Change e.g. data entry error. Save the instrument once all changes are saved.

Auto-Numbering for Records

The first field on the first instrument of a project will always be the record ID which cannot be edited and cannot be moved to another instrument. In the project, navigate to the 'Patient Details' form and you will see that the first field is the Record ID, The Record ID is a field that cannot be edited by the user:

Record ID	3
Study ID:	<input type="text"/>

Note: For the next section we will be referring to the 'Patient Details' Instrument in the GW4 project.

4.2 Field Types

There are 14 field types available in REDCap and we will now go through how each type can be used for standard data collection.

Text box

The first questions on the 'Patient Details' form (**First name** and **Last name**) are examples of text boxes, which is the best option when collecting single-line text (for text and numbers).

These fields have no validation, enabling users to enter text in any format, but they are required fields so users must provide an answer.

The 'Email' question is also a text box, but this has been validated as an email field, so that users can only input an email address in the correct format and will receive an alert if it does not follow the expected format.

Date of birth is another text box that has been validated to only be accepted if entered as DD/MM/YYYY. The user can choose to select the date using the calendar icon to the right of the field (as below), or to enter it manually. Again, they will receive an alert if it does not follow the expected format.

You can also set minimum and maximum values for date fields for further validation. For example, the date of birth field has a maximum value of 'today' to ensure that participants cannot enter a birth date in the future:

Notes Box is a text box that allows you to capture more than just one line of text. An example of a notes box can be found at the bottom of the *Patient Details* page.

Multiple choice fields

There are two options for multiple choice answers: **Drop down list** and **Radio buttons** which are used for single answer responses.

The question '**Current gender identity**' is an example of a drop-down list, whilst the question '**Gender assigned at birth**' is an example of a radio button.

Checkboxes allow users to select multiple answers to a question and are useful when more than one answer can be selected:

For all multiple-choice fields you must enter the answer options in the 'Choices' box. REDCap will automatically associate a number with each option (which will show in the records when exporting data in 'raw' format).

During development the options can be coded manually, by assigning each option to a number by entering the coded number and a comma before the choice label e.g.:

Note: For the next set of field types, we will refer to the 'Screening Log' instrument in the test REDCap project.

Yes – No fields only allow the answer to be Yes or No. All of the fields in the Eligibility criteria section of the instrument are this field type.

True – False fields act in the same way as the Yes - No fields, so they can both be used to fit the question context. For example, the '**Is the patient eligible?**' field is a True – False field, but this could also be a Yes – No field.

Signature fields allow users to scribe their name using a tablet or mouse and is saved as a .png file which is downloadable (see the '*Clinician Signature*' field on the instrument).

File Upload fields allow users to upload any associated files or images that may need to be attached to individual records. These documents are only associated with that record and cannot be accessed anywhere else in the project.

This feature allows a new file to be uploaded into a field that already has a file uploaded into it. If a file has already been uploaded, the field will show a 'Upload new version' link:

This allows the user to upload another file without having to delete the existing one. The old/existing file will not be deleted, and will still be accessible in the Data History popup (by clicking the "H" icon next to the field):

Within the Data History popup, all versions of the file will be displayed in a table format and listed in chronological order with regard to the date it was uploaded. Users may view, download, or delete any existing version of each file:

Date/Time of Upload	User	File Uploaded	File Version	Information / Action
03-10-2023 10:56:03	charli.grimes	Upload File - "Consent form 2023 V.2.docx"	V1	Deleted on 03-10-2023 10:57
03-10-2023 10:56:40	charli.grimes	Upload File - "Consent form 2023.docx"	V2	Download Delete
03-10-2023 10:56:58 (most recent data change)	charli.grimes	Upload File - "Consent form 2023 V.2.docx"	V3	Download Delete

Note: You must save the form in order for the file to be saved within the record.

Calculated fields allow you to make real-time calculations on data entry instruments and surveys, based on other fields in the project.

Slider / Visual Analogue Scale

This field works best when collecting data directly from participants as the answer is collected on a sliding scale, coded as values 0-100. You can customise it to add labels above the left, middle and right sides of the slider, and you can hide the value associated with the answer. There is an example of this field type on the *Questionnaire* instrument.

Descriptive text fields are great for starting a section where you need to add additional information, but no answer is required.

Begin new section fields are used to separate different sections of an instrument and are used for organisation purposes only. You can add text to serve as a header or leave it blank. No variable name is required for this field, and it will not be exported in a report. Please note that these fields cannot be the first or the last fields on an instrument.

For example, on the Screening Log Instrument, all of the sections in yellow (e.g. **Eligibility Criteria** and **Eligibility Summary**) are to begin new sections and describe what the section of the form is for.

4.3 Instrument Status

Every REDCap instrument has a form status indicator at the bottom of the form. Users can set the value of this during data entry as either Incomplete, Unverified or Complete regardless of the status of the data entry e.g. an instrument can be marked as complete despite missing mandatory fields.

The screenshot shows a 'Form Status' dropdown menu with the following options: Complete (selected), Incomplete, Unverified, and Complete. A red box highlights the dropdown menu.

Each study team should decide what these statuses mean for them based on their local policy but some suggestions as to how these should be used are as follows:

Marking a form as **'Incomplete'** the user indicates to the rest of the study team that there are missing fields in the form which will need to be completed later. These forms will be marked with a red icon on the record status dashboard.

Marking a form as **'Unverified'** the user indicates that all the data has been collected but an internal review (potentially by the PI/CI) is required. The record should remain as unverified until the review is complete, at which point they can be moved to 'Complete'. Forms with this status will appear with a yellow dot on the record status dashboard.

Marking a form as **'Complete'** the user indicates that all the data has been collected and verified. Forms with this status will appear with a green dot on the record status dashboard.

When an instrument is completed as a survey, the icons appear with a tick in the dashboard. Green icons with a tick indicates that the survey response has been completed and all data has been collected.

Those with an orange icon and a tick indicates that there is a partial survey response and some data is still missing from the form.

Finally, instruments that are associated with a grey circle indicates that no data has been saved. There is also a legend for each status icon on the Record Status Dashboard for your reference:

4.4 Saving and Warning Messages

As previously mentioned, branching logic can be used to show fields that are purely designed to give information to the person doing data entry and are not used to collect data.

It is good practice for projects to have standard formatting/colours across the REDCap projects so users can quickly identify whether the field is a warning or information field etc.

On the below screenshot from the **Patient Details** instrument, there is an information message at the bottom of the page which will only show when all the required fields have been completed:

Please mark the form as 'Complete' below and Save it

This instructs the user to mark the form as complete, indicating that all necessary fields have been completed and no further information is required.

Conversely, warning messages can be set up with a red background, to catch the user's eye. For example, on the *Screening Log* instrument, there are several fields which will trigger a warning that the participant is not eligible for the study. Equally there is descriptive text under each question in red font which shows which fields are mandatory:

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Aged between 18 - 60 Yes No
* must provide value reset

If answer is 'NO' the patient is NOT eligible for the study

Has the patient undergone any previous spinal surgery? Yes No
* must provide value reset

If answer is 'NO' the patient is NOT eligible for the study

Does the patient have a known suspected underlying disease? Yes No
* must provide value reset

If answer is 'YES' the patient is NOT eligible for the study

4.5 Viewing an Instrument as a Survey

When collecting data, it is expected that participants will complete surveys through the survey link provided and for research nurses to be completing data entry through their own REDCap login. However, when a data collection instrument has been enabled as a survey, it is possible to enter data by viewing it in survey mode through your REDCap login.

To see how the survey will appear to participants in a survey, open the instrument you are collecting data in, then click on the 'Survey options' icon in the top right corner:

Data Access Group: [No Assignment] ?

Invitation status: Survey options

Editing existing Record ID 1.

Event: **Screening**

Record ID: 1

Survey options

- Open survey
- Log out + Open survey
- Compose survey invitation
- Survey Access Code + QR Code

Then select 'Open survey'.

This will bring the survey up in a new window through which data can be entered. This is useful when you are designing your instrument to see how it appears to participants.

Note: When data is entered through a personal REDCap login, an audit trail is kept through the 'logging' function. However, when data is collected via a survey, there is no user saved against survey in the audit trail, so best practice is to use a REDCap login for data entry done by research staff, where possible.

!!Warning!!

For this reason, study teams should not complete participant surveys as it is unclear on who has entered the data.

5. User roles

User roles can be used to assign privileges to site staff. Developers/trial teams can set user roles based on what site staff should/shouldn't be able to do within the trial based on a signed delegation log.

There are two different types of permissions you can assign: 'Basic Privileges'; and 'Privileges for Viewing and Exporting Data'.

5.1 Basic User Privileges

Basic Privileges

Highest level privileges:

- Project Design and Setup
- User Rights
- Data Access Groups

Other privileges:

- Survey Distribution Tools
- Alerts & Notifications
- Calendar
- Add/Edit/Organize Reports
Also allows user to view ALL reports (but not necessarily all data in the reports)
- Stats & Charts
- Data Import Tool
- Data Comparison Tool
- Logging
- File Repository
- Data Quality
[What is Data Quality?](#)
- API
[What is the REDCap API?](#)

Settings pertaining to the REDCap Mobile App:

- REDCap Mobile App
[What is the REDCap Mobile App?](#)
- Allow user to collect data offline in the mobile app
- Allow user to download data for all records to the app?

Settings pertaining to project records: [Explain these settings](#)

- Create Records
- Rename Records
- Delete Records
* Includes ability to delete all data on an instrument or on a repeating event.

Settings pertaining to record locking and E-signatures:

- Record Locking Customization
- Lock/Unlock Records (instrument level)
Users with locking privileges also have access to the E-signature and Locking Mgmt page on the left-hand Applications menu.
[Watch video about locking](#)
- Disabled
- Locking / Unlocking
- Locking / Unlocking with E-signature authority
[What is an E-signature?](#)
- Lock/Unlock *Entire* Records (record level)

Settings pertaining to the REDCap Mobile App:

- Create & edit rules
- Execute rules
- API Export
- API Import/Update

Settings pertaining to the REDCap Mobile App:

- REDCap Mobile App
[What is the REDCap Mobile App?](#)
- Allow user to collect data offline in the mobile app
- Allow user to download data for all records to the app?

Settings pertaining to project records: [Explain these settings](#)

- Create Records
- Rename Records
- Delete Records
* Includes ability to delete all data on an instrument or on a repeating event.

Settings pertaining to record locking and E-signatures:

- Record Locking Customization
- Lock/Unlock Records (instrument level)
Users with locking privileges also have access to the E-signature and Locking Mgmt page on the left-hand Applications menu.
[Watch video about locking](#)
- Disabled
- Locking / Unlocking
- Locking / Unlocking with E-signature authority
[What is an E-signature?](#)
- Lock/Unlock *Entire* Records (record level)

NOTE: It is important to note that instrument level locking and record level locking are independent features that are governed by separate user privileges (as seen above). You must have explicit permission to either one in order to perform that specific locking action. Also, record locking is a higher-level locking than instrument locking, which means that an entire record may be locked or unlocked while one or more instruments are currently locked, but an instrument cannot be locked or unlocked while the entire record is locked.

These are higher level privileges to do with the functionality of the database/project such as the design and set up and need to be carefully assigned. By selecting or deselecting the boxes you can assign these rights to the roles. Please see the above privileges for reference.

5.2 Viewing and Exporting Privileges

Privileges for Viewing and Exporting Data								
Data Viewing Rights pertain to a user's ability to view or edit data on pages in the project (e.g., data entry forms, reports). Users with 'No Access' Data Viewing Rights for a given instrument will not be able to view that instrument for any record, nor will they be able to view fields from that instrument on a report. Data Export Rights pertain to a user's ability to export data from the project, whether through the Data Exports page, API, Mobile App, or in PDFs of instruments containing record data. Note: Data Viewing Rights and Data Export Rights are completely separate and do not impact one another.								
	Data Viewing Rights				Data Export Rights			
	No Access (Hidden)	Read Only	View & Edit	Edit survey responses	No Access	De-Identified*	Remove All Identifier Fields	Full Data Set
Pre-Screening (survey)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Eligibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Randomisation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Treatment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Withdrawal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Note to File	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

* De-identified means that all free-form text fields will be removed, as well as any date/time fields and Identifier fields.

Privileges for viewing and exporting data can also be assigned based on the different forms within the project. Access can be restricted by viewing and exporting privileges which can help with assigning blinded and unblinded roles.

Privileges for Viewing and Exporting Data								
Data Viewing Rights pertain to a user's ability to view or edit data on pages in the project (e.g., data entry forms, reports). Users with 'No Access' Data Viewing Rights for a given instrument will not be able to view that instrument for any record, nor will they be able to view fields from that instrument on a report. Data Export Rights pertain to a user's ability to export data from the project, whether through the Data Exports page, API, Mobile App, or in PDFs of instruments containing record data. Note: Data Viewing Rights and Data Export Rights are completely separate and do not impact one another.								
	Data Viewing Rights				Data Export Rights			
	No Access (Hidden)	Read Only	View & Edit	Edit survey responses	No Access	De-Identified*	Remove All Identifier Fields	Full Data Set
Pre-Screening (survey)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Eligibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Randomisation	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Treatment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Withdrawal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Note to File	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

By selecting no access (hidden) you can hide this form from view on the record status dashboard. You can make forms read-only or enable full editing rights.

For data exports you can select how much, if any, data can be exported by the different user roles. De-identified refers to all free-form text fields will be removed, as well as any date/time fields and identifier fields. Remove all identifier fields will only remove these fields excluding date/time and free-form text. So both go from right to left- full access to most restricted/no access.

If survey options have been enabled within the project, you can also select what roles can 'edit survey responses'.

In this example, the PI role cannot access the Randomisation instrument and has read-only access to Eligibility.

If you go back into the 'Record Status Dashboard' you can see that the randomisation form is missing from the selection.

For read-only displays, using the Eligibility form; fields are all greyed out and cannot be clicked on to edit data. This applies to new and existing forms.

[+ Add new record](#)

Displaying: [Instrument status only](#) | [Lock status only](#) | [All status types](#)

Record ID	Screening				Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
	Pre-Screening	Eligibility	Withdrawal	Note to File	Treatment	Treatment	Treatment
1	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
2	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Eligibility

Editing existing Record ID 1.

Event: **Screening**

Record ID: 1

First name: * must provide value

Aged between 18 - 60 Yes No * must provide value

What the patient given the Patient Information Leaflet? Yes No * must provide value

Date form completed:

Form Status

Complete? -- Cancel --

For more information about creating and assigning user roles please see the Advanced user guide.

6. Data Access Groups (DAGs)

6.1 What is a Data Access Group?

A Data Access Group (DAG) is a way of separating and grouping users from different organisations so that they can view and edit the data that is collected for participants within their organisation in line with GDPR and GCP. It is common to have multiple DAGs acting as different sites within a study.

Whilst in a DAG, when you add records the site ID will be prefixed to any record IDs created, see below: 823 is associated with the DAG, then sequential number denoted by the hyphen. The DAG is also specified in the 'Data collection' section.

NEW Record ID 823-1

Data Collection Instrument	Screening	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Pre-Screening (survey)	<input type="radio"/>			
Eligibility	<input type="radio"/>			
Randomisation	<input type="radio"/>			
Treatment		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Withdrawal	<input type="radio"/>			
Note to File	<input type="radio"/>			

6.2 How to switch between DAGs

If you have been assigned to multiple DAGs you can use the blue toolbar at the top of the screen to switch between DAGs. By selecting 'switch' you can select another DAG to access:

Once the other DAG has been selected it will show in the user rights section:

Role name <small>(click role name to edit role)</small>	Username or users assigned to a role <small>(click username to edit or assign to role)</small>	Expiration <small>(click expiration date to edit)</small>	Data Access Group	Pr D S
—	sophie.rose (Sophie Rose)	never	Bristol University	
Administrator	[No users from your group are assigned]			

This is particularly helpful when research assistants/nurses etc are recruiting for multiple sites within a study. **It is very important however that sites are aware they can switch using this tool and to make sure they have selected the correct DAG before entering any data into the project.**

Once the DAG has been changed and a new record ID is created, the record ID will reflect the DAG number as well as the participant ID within that DAG.

After creating a new record, you can also switch DAGs by form using the drop down. However, when doing this, the DAG ID is not assigned with the record ID.

7. Surveys

Surveys can be used for participants to complete questionnaires dependent on how the project is setup. REDCap can email a survey link directly to the participant's specified email address for their completion. The data is entered directly into the instrument in REDCap.

The survey links can either be one-time use or re-accessed and edited by the participant, depending on how the project is setup.

8. Data Resolution Workflow

This function allows users to open a workflow to document the process of resolving issues with data within the project. Users can identify fields that may contain questionable data and draw it to the attention of data entry users to check.

Please contact your administrator if this function is not enabled.

8.1 Initiating a Data Query and Identifying Incorrect Data

Whilst reviewing data entry you may notice that something does not look right. If this is the case, you can open a query by clicking on the speech bubble to the left of the answer.

Note: *If it's the first-time data has been entered into the form, it will need to be saved first to create the record, before clicking the speech bubble icon.*

Clicking the speech bubble icon will open a pop-up window:

You can either verify the data, which will confirm that it is correct, or open a new query.

Once opened, you can assign it to a specific user, and choose whether to notify them of this by email.

Then write the comment. An example of a data query in our project is given below:

Data Resolution Workflow ✕

[VIDEO: Data Resolution Workflow](#)

This pop-up displays the Data Resolution Workflow for the specified record for a given field and/or Data Quality rule. Users with appropriate user privileges may open data queries to begin a documented process of resolving an issue with the data. Opened data queries may thus be responded to by users with appropriate privileges, and then they may be closed once the issue has been resolved. All data queries can also be viewed on the Resolve Issues page in this project.

Record ID: **1**
 Event: **Baseline**
 Field: **pq_ic_crm_yn** ("Do you like ice cream?")
 Status: **Not Opened**

Date/Time	User	Comments and Details
20-09-2023 11:48	[survey respondent]	Data Changes Made: pq_ic_crm_yn = 'Yes (1)'
04-10-2023 09:31	charli.grimes	<input type="radio"/> Verified data value — OR — <input checked="" type="radio"/> Open query Assign query to a user (optional): <input type="text" value="gw4.study.team (GW4 St..."/> Notify this user of their assignment using: <input type="checkbox"/> Email <input type="checkbox"/> REDCap Messenger Comment: <input style="width: 100%;" type="text" value="Participant has previously stated that they are lactose intolerant"/>

When viewing the record, it will be clear that there is a data query associated with that field as it will be highlighted, and the speech bubble will have a red exclamation mark in it:

8.2 Finding and Resolving Queries

To see any data queries, navigate to the left navigation panel and click on the 'Resolve Issues' icon, under Applications:

This will show all queries in the database. Gives record number, what the field type is, if assigned to user, how long open and what the update was and what the most recent update was:

Data Resolution Dashboard						
Filters: Open / unresolved issues (3)						
All fields and rules						
All events						
User assigned (all users) or not assigned						
Click button to view data query	Record	Data Quality rule and/or Field	User Assigned	Days Open	First Update	Last Update
1 comment	1 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pq_ic_crm_yn (Do you like ice cream?)	gw4.study.team	0	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:32): "Participant has previously stated that they are lactose intolerant"	[same as first update]
1 comment	1 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	0	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:40): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]
1 comment	2 Bristol Bristol Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	0	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:43): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]

You can use the drop-down menu at the top to sort your data queries on their status:

8.3 Working on an Issue

Click on the comment icon to see what the issue is:

1 comment	1 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pq_ic_crm_yn (Do you like ice cream?)	gw4.study.team	0	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:32): "Participant has previously stated that they are lactose intolerant"	[same as first update]
-----------	-------------------------------	--	----------------	---	---	------------------------

To navigate to the queried variable you can select the record ID which will take you to the form and query to correct the data entered.

You can either choose default response or close the query, but you must always write a comment in the box to explain the steps you have taken to resolve the issues:

Date/Time	User	Comments and Details
20-09-2023 11:48	[survey respondent]	Data Changes Made: pq_ic_crm_yn = 'Yes (1)'
04-10-2023 09:32	charli.grimes	Action: Opened query Assigned to user: gw4.study.team (GW4 Study Team) Comment: "Participant has previously stated that they are lactose intolerant" Assign to other user
04-10-2023 09:47	charli.grimes	<input type="radio"/> Reply with response: Corrected - Wrong source used Upload file (optional): Upload file — OR — <input checked="" type="radio"/> Close the query Comment: Checked with the participant and they are not lactose intolerant

You can also upload documentation to support response using the 'Upload file' link.

Closing the query will mark it as requiring no further action and it will disappear from the open/unresolved filter. If you reply with a response, it will be sent back to the user who opened it for further attention either via email or redcap messenger- this can be selected/specified when working in the query window

It is worth noting that users are assigned permissions to be able to open/close and respond to queries, therefore you may not be able to complete all of the above actions in your own projects.

8.4 Bookmarking Data Queries

If you just want to see the issues assigned to you, take the specific URL, and 'Set up project bookmarks' under 'Project Setup':

Once this is set up, you will be able to see them on the left navigation panel:

9. Data Quality

The Data Quality section allows you to execute data quality rules upon your project data to check for discrepancies in your data.

The Data Quality section can be found in the left-hand navigation under 'Applications'.

Table 1: Data Quality section on left hand keys menu

When you click on the Data Quality section, the Data Quality matrix table displays under the first tab 'Find Issues'. All rules are recorded against headings. The rules displayed in dark red font are default data rules. To run the data quality rule, click on the Execute button.

Enabling the 'real-time execution' functionality (shown by the green tick against list of consented ppts) for a Custom Rule checks if the data is entered correctly in real-time once 'Save' is pressed* instead of retrospectively using the 'real-time execution' feature is an excellent way to be proactive about maintaining the quality and integrity of your data.

Rule #	Rule Name	Rule Logic (Show discrepancy only if...)	Real-time execution	Total Discrepancies	Delete rule?
A	Blank values*			Execute	
B	Blank values* (required fields only)			Execute	
C	Field validation errors (incorrect data type)			Execute	
D	Field validation errors (out of range)			Execute	
E	Outliers for numerical fields (numbers, integers, sliders, calc fields)**			Execute	
F	Hidden fields that contain values***			Execute	
G	Multiple choice fields with invalid values			Execute	
H	Incorrect values for calculated fields			Execute	
I	Fields containing "missing data codes"			Execute	
1	List of consented ppts undergone spinal surgery	[s1_sprn]="1" AND [s1_cnsnt]="1"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Execute	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Add	<input type="text"/> Enter descriptive name for new rule (e.g., Participants below age 18)	<input type="text"/> Enter logic for new rule (e.g., [age] < 18) How do I use special functions?	<input type="checkbox"/> Execute in real time on data entry forms ?
------------	--	---	--

Table 2: Data Quality inbuilt rules

To run the data quality rule in 'real-time,' once save is pressed, click in the box under 'Real time execution.' The green tick will show this has been enabled against this rule. Further guidance can be accessed by clicking on the question mark next to the heading.

NOTE: The pre-defined rules cannot have 'real-time execution' enabled, but only the custom rules can. Also, the 'real-time execution' functionality does not work on survey pages, nor does it get executed when performing data imports (either via the Data Import Tool or via the API). Thus, it only works on data entry forms.

Rule #	Rule Name	Rule Logic (Show discrepancy only if...)	Real-time execution <input type="checkbox"/>	Total Discrepancies	Delete rule?
A	Blank values*	-		Execute	
B	Blank values* (required fields only)	-		Execute	
C	Field validation errors (incorrect data type)	-		Execute	
D	Field validation errors (out of range)	-		Execute	
E	Outliers for numerical fields (numbers, integers, sliders, calc fields)**	-		Execute	
F	Hidden fields that contain values***	-		Execute	
G	Multiple choice fields with invalid values	-		Execute	
H	Incorrect values for calculated fields	-		Execute	
I	Fields containing "missing data codes"	-		Execute	
1	List of consented ppts undergone spinal surgery	[sl_spn]="1" AND [sl_cnsnt]="1"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Execute	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Add	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Enter descriptive name for new rule (e.g., Participants below age 18)	Enter logic for new rule (e.g., [age] < 18) How do I use special functions?	Execute in real time on data entry forms <input type="checkbox"/>

Table 3: Data Quality rules manually created.

You may also create your own rules by clicking on the green Add button, entering the rule name, the rule logic (if known) and save, or edit, delete (click on the red cross; this can only be done for custom rules, default rules cannot be deleted), or reorder the rules you have already created by drag and drop.

Data Quality Rules ✔ Processing Complete! Execute rules:

- Upload or download Data Quality Rules ▾
 - Upload Data Quality Rule (CSV)
 - Download Data Quality Rule (CSV)
- Apply to: All Records ▾

Rule #	Rule Name	Rule Logic (Show discrepancy only if...)	Real-time execution ?	Total Discrepancies	Delete rule?
A	Blank values*	-		40 export view	
B	Blank values* (required fields only)	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
C	Field validation errors (incorrect data type)	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
D	Field validation errors (out of range)	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
E	Outliers for numerical fields (numbers, integers, sliders, calc fields)**	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
F	Hidden fields that contain values***	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
G	Multiple choice fields with invalid values	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
H	Incorrect values for calculated fields	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
I	Fields containing "missing data codes"	-		<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	
1	List of consented ppts undergone spinal surgery	[s1_spnl]="1" AND [s1_cnsnt]="1"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Save	<input type="button" value="Execute"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="button" value="Add"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Enter descriptive name for new rule (e.g., Participants below age 18)	Enter logic for new rule (e.g., [age] < 18) How do I use special functions?	Execute in real time on data entry forms ?		

Table 4: Reports upload/download option; Real time data entry save option.

Once the rule is run, if any data violates the data quality rule e.g. blank values, a warning pop-up message will list all data quality rules that have been violated, and also display the fields involved with their data values. If no rules were violated, then it will save the record as usual and not display a pop-up message. Just like the results that are returned when executing rules on the Data Quality page itself, results displayed on data entry forms for 'real-time execution' can be excluded (if desired) so that they will not be displayed again if they are still in violation in the future.

click the "Execute All Rules" button to fire all the rules at once. This will provide you with a total number of discrepancies found for each rule and will allow you to view the details of those discrepancies by clicking the 'View' link next to each.

Data reports can be uploaded or downloaded in csv format by using the buttons in the top-right.

Table 5: Data Quality rules commands

Note: Rule H should only ever be executed by development team, due to the unpredictable effect.

Table 6: resolved issues tab 2 in data quality section.

The 'Resolved issues' tab is the second tab in the Data Quality section which covers the queries listing and action taken.

Table 7: View option's expanded view

The above screenshot shows the expanded visual of data quality rules in the 'view' option for reports. Point 1 highlights says the name of the reports, point 2 is the number of the records fulfilling report

criteria in this case it is number of discrepancies. Point 3 is the option to export report in csv format. In records 4 is site name/number, 2 is participant number, 6 is details of the record found with the value and raised issue, 7 shows type of issue and status of issue, 8 is comment box where response updated on queries can be seen. 9 point says the visit/event query was raised on.

Table 8: Resolve issues tab in data quality section

Tab 2 in the Data Quality section details the resolved issue as shown in table 8. This tab contains the listing of open/actioned issues raised. This information can be exported in csv report format. It has multiple filters to select and narrow down options to view. The Comment box shows the responses recorded on issues. The update columns give details about the queries, who has raised them and when.

Table 9: Data resolution workflow view

Once the comment box as shown in table 9 is clicked on, a data resolution workflow popup opens; this displays information about the comments response, who has responded and raised queries and the time.

Data Resolution Workflow
✕

[VIDEO: Data Resolution Workflow](#)

This pop-up displays the Data Resolution Workflow for the specified record for a given field and/or Data Quality rule. Users with appropriate user privileges may open data queries to begin a documented process of resolving an issue with the data. Opened data queries may thus be responded to by users with appropriate privileges, and then they may be closed once the issue has been resolved. All data queries can also be viewed on the Resolve Issues page in this project.

Record ID: **1**
 Event: **Baseline**
 Field: **pt_nmbr** ("Mobile Number:")
 Status: 🗨️ **Open / Unresolved** (unresponded)

Date/Time	User	Comments and Details
04-10-2023 09:40	charli.grimes	Data Changes Made: pt_nmbr = '0799923918'
04-10-2023 09:40	charli.grimes	Action: Opened query Assigned to user: gw4.study.team (GW4 Study Team) Comment: "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"

⚠️ Awaiting action by user with sufficient user privileges.

Table 10: Data resolution expanded tab with open queries

Table 10 shows the section containing query specific details such as event/visit, Record ID, participants number and status of the query.

Below tables 11, 12, 13 & 14 shows the details about the available filters for the data resolution dashboard.

Data Resolution Dashboard

Export

Filters: Open / unresolved issues (2) ▼

Click button to view data query	Record	Data Quality and/or Field	Assigned	Days Open	First Update	Last Update
🗨️ 1 comment	1 Bristol BRS004 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.2	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:40): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]
🗨️ 1 comment	2 Bristol BRS004 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.2	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:43): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]

Table 11: Data resolution dashboard filter-1

Data Resolution Dashboard Filters: Open / unresolved issues (2) ▾

Export

Click button to view data query

Record	Data Quality and/or Field	User Assigned	Days Open	First Update	Last Update
1 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.3	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:40): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]
2 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.3	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:43): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]

Table 12:Data resolution dashboard filter-2

Data Resolution Dashboard Filters: Open / unresolved issues (2) ▾

Export

Click button to view data query

Record	Data Quality and/or Field	User Assigned	Days Open	First Update	Last Update
1 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.3	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:40): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]
2 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.3	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:43): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]

Table 13:Data resolution dashboard filter-3

Data Resolution Dashboard Filters: Open / unresolved issues (2) ▾

Export

Click button to view data query

Record	Data Quality and/or Field	User Assigned	Days Open	First Update	Last Update
1 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	34.3	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:40): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]
2 Bristol BRS00 Baseline	Field: pt_nmbr (Mobile Number:)	gw4.study.team	35	charli.grimes (04-10-2023 09:43): "Mobile number doesn't look like it has enough digits"	[same as first update]

Table 14:Data resolution dashboard filter-4

Tab 3 in the Data Quality module can be used to make a visual presentation of the data reports executed.

Table 15:Resolution metrics tab

10. Reporting

10.1 REDCap Project Types

There are two types of REDCap project:

- Standard Project
- "Longitudinal data collection with defined events" Project

10.2 Standard Projects

Standard projects consist of several instruments, each of which is only completed once for each participant. There is also an option for "repeating instruments" for forms that may repeat a variable number of times such as "File Note" or "Contact Log". This structure is used for simple projects such as those containing participant contact details. It is not appropriate for projects with questionnaires that repeat at specific timepoints.

10.3 Longitudinal Data Collection with Defined Events Project

The most commonly used project structure is the "longitudinal data collection with defined events" which is used for the main participant pathway in a trial, including questionnaires. It should be noted that in REDCap reporting that a row in the report represents a single participant for a single event. If you wish to output details for a participant at three different timepoints then there will be three rows in the report.

10.4 Structural Limitations

It is not possible to combine fields from different events in the same output row in a REDCap report. This can be problematic when the study ID is not the primary key for the record as it will likely be stored in a field in the primary event and therefore will not be available in any reports that exclusively use the subsequent events such as questionnaires.

One solution to this is to ensure that when instruments are entered in subsequent events that there are hidden fields that duplicate values from the primary event that may be useful in reporting, study ID in particular. The weakness of this strategy is that it requires a form to be saved in each follow-up event and also that an amendment to the value in the first event will not automatically be replicated to subsequent events. A more flexible solution to this would be to have a data entry trigger (DET) function that replicates values from the first form whenever it is saved but that requires bespoke code to be written.

10.4 Totals and Sub-totals

REDCap is only able to report how many rows were returned and cannot calculate column totals or sub-totals. For more sophisticated reporting, data should be exported to a statistical package such as Stata.

10.5 Creating a REDCap Report

Click on "Data Exports, Reports and Stats":

Click on the button "+ Create New Report":

Name of Report:	<input type="text"/>
Set as "public":	<p>Enabling this feature below will auto-generate a public link for viewing the report without needing to log in to REDCap.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Report is publicly viewable by anyone with the public link</p>
Description (optional): Displayed on page below report name	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>Paragraph ↶ ↷</p> <p> ☰ ☱ ☲ ☳ ☴ ☵ ☶ ☷ A ▾ Q <> I ↺ ↻ </p> </div>

Name of Report

This should summarise the purpose of the report.

Set as "public"

Depending on how the REDCap instance is configured, public access may or may not be possible. Most REDCap instances allow completion of surveys by participants so those would allow this setting to be used. Some REDCap instances are secured by university firewalls, VPNs and logins so selecting "public" in that scenario would only allow restricted access.

Description

This should describe in greater detail how the report works and what it is to be used for.

Step 1

This is where edit and view access to the report is set.

STEP 1

+ User Access: Choose who can edit and view this report

View Access: Choose who sees this report on their left-hand project menu [?](#)

All users - OR - **Custom user access** (Choose specific users, roles, or data access groups who will have access)

Edit Access: Choose who can edit, copy, or delete this report (requires user to have 'Add/Edit/Organize Reports' privileges)

All users - OR - **Custom user access** (Choose specific users, roles, or data access groups who will have access)

10.6 View Access

Often the person creating a report needs it to be available to others to run. Access can be given to specific users or user roles. It is recommended to use "User Roles" as that is more flexible and will not entail needing to change permissions when a staff member leaves and is replaced.

+ User Access: Choose who can edit and view this report

View Access: Choose who sees this report on their left-hand project menu [?](#)

All users - OR - **Custom user access** (Users in ANY groups selected below will have access)

Selected users

- gw4.study.team (GW4 Study Team)
- martin.house (Martin House)
- nm.almuina (Nuria Marquez Almuina)
- pooja.ghorpade (Pooja Ghorpade)

Selected user roles

- Administrator
- No Access
- Site Staff
- Statistician

View a list of users who will have access to this report based on the selections above: [View user access list](#)

10.7 Edit Access

Similar to View access, it is recommended that "Edit Access" be restricted to the user role that the person creating the report is in. This will (for example) allow new trial managers to edit the reports of their predecessors.

Edit Access: Choose who can edit, copy, or delete this report (requires user to have 'Add/Edit/Organize Reports' privileges)

All users - OR - **Custom user access** (Users in ANY groups selected below will have access)

Selected users

- gw4.study.team (GW4 Study Team)
- martin.house (Martin House)
- nm.almuina (Nuria Marquez Almuina)
- pooja.ghorpade (Pooja Ghorpade)

Selected user roles

- Administrator
- No Access
- Site Staff
- Statistician

View a list of users who will have access to this report based on the selections above: [View user access list](#)

Step 2

This is where the required fields for the report are selected.

These can be selected using the dropdowns displayed in Step 2. However, a much quicker way to select fields is by using the "Quick Add" button as below:

Once fields have been selected, their sequence can be changed by dragging them in the Step 2 list.

10.8 Additional Report Options

- Include the survey identifier field and survey timestamp field(s)?

When an instrument is completed as a survey then REDCap automatically generates a timestamp on completion. This can be displayed by selecting this option.

- Combine checkbox options into single column of only the checked-off options (will be formatted as a text field when exported to stats packages)

By default checkboxes are output as if each selected option is a separate field. This allows that to be over-ridden so that multiple values can be displayed in a single field.

- Remove line breaks/carriage returns from all text data values (only applicable for CSV Raw and CSV Label data exports)

Sometimes the use of line breaks and carriage returns can cause problems when exported data is imported into other software, so this allows for them to be omitted from the output

- In the report header, display the field label, variable, or both (not applicable for exports)?

- In the report's data, display the field label, raw data value, or both for multiple choice fields (not applicable for exports)?

This is a very important point to note. Although labels for coded values can be displayed on screen in a report only the actual code value is included in an output file.

Step 3

The pre-selection of the first checkbox here is the most frequent cause of reports not producing the expected output. If this box is ticked, then all other filter settings relating to events will be ignored and everything will be output.

STEP 3

Show data for all events for each record returned [How to use filters and AND/OR logic](#)

Filters (optional) **Operator / Value**

Filter 1	Type variable name or field label ⌵		= ⌵	
	in ⌵			
	All events ⌵			

Switch format: [Use advanced logic](#)

Additional Filters (optional) (Records belonging only to ALL selections below will appear in the report)

Filter by event(s):	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;"> Admin ▲ Baseline ▼ </div>
----------------------------	--

Live Filters (optional) Live Filters can be selected on the report page for dynamically filtering data in real time. With the exception of the Record ID field, only multiple choice fields can be used as Live Filters (as well as Events, if longitudinal, and Data Access Groups, if any exist).

Live Filter 1	-- select a field -- ⌵
Live Filter 2	-- select a field -- ⌵
Live Filter 3	-- select a field -- ⌵

Selecting a field from the drop-down for "Filter 1" allows record selection to be limited based upon the value of the selected field. Additional filters can be added to select based on multiple criteria using AND/OR.

However, for more sophisticated record selection there is the option "Use advanced logic". One useful tip for using this function is to first use the simple Filter selection to select all of the fields that you wish (entering any values in Operator/Value before pressing the "Use advanced logic" button. You will then have the exact field names that you require and can just focus on the selection syntax.

10.9 Why Use Advanced Logic?

There are two main things that we can do in "Advanced" mode that aren't available in Simple mode:

1. **Field Value Comparison** - directly compare one field value to another field value looking for matched or unmatched.
2. **Date Difference Calculation** - the period between 2 stored dates or between a stored date and the current date.

10.10 Field Value Comparison Example

Here is an example comparing two text fields to see if they match:

Filters (optional)

Advanced filter logic: (e.g., [age] > 30 and [sex] = "1") [How do I use special functions?](#)

`[event-name][crt_usr_nm_dflt] <> [event-name][updt_usr_nm]`

✔ **Valid** (The determination of validity may not be 100% accurate in all contexts.)

Perhaps the most useful option is for comparing a date to the current date to identify which participants currently require a follow-up action by the trial team. Here is an example comparing a datetime field to the current date and time:

You can calculate the difference between two dates or times by using the “datediff” function.

10.11 Date Difference Calculation Example

Here is an example selecting all participants recruited between 4 and 6 weeks ago:

Filters (optional)

Advanced filter logic: (e.g., [age] > 30 and [sex] = "1") [How do I use special functions?](#)

`datediff([event-name][created_dt],'today','d','dmy',true) >= 28 and
datediff([event-name][created_dt],'today','d','dmy',true) <= 42`

✔ **Valid** (The determination of validity may not be 100% accurate in all contexts.)

As indicated above, it is always good practice to specify the last parameter as “true”. If this parameter is not specified (or specifically set to false) then the selection would also include any records where the calculation produced a result of 4 – 6 weeks *in the future*!

Using two “datediff” statements to set upper and lower limits to the selection is usually a prudent choice. This way the volume of records output by the report will not keep rising, unless that is specifically what you want it to do (e.g. All recruitments since date X). In practice, a good example would be for sending a survey invite for a 3-month questionnaire. As well as checking that 3 months have passed since recruitment, it should also check that we haven’t already gotten closer to the text timepoint (perhaps 6 months) and therefore this is no longer appropriate to send. Late data entry can offer trigger survey invites if no maximum send date has been given.

This example calculates in days, but other units are available:

Units

"y"	years	1 year = 365.2425 days
"M"	months	1 month = 30.44 days
"d"	days	
"h"	hours	
"m"	minutes	
"s"	seconds	

*NB. Please note from this table that REDCap can only approximate a month or a year in calculations but is **precise if days or weeks** are used. This should be considered in the protocol as perhaps monthly intervals can be avoided.*

10.12 Additional Filters (optional)

This is very useful to select only the timepoints that will contain the data items you wish to see in your report. There are basically three types of selection here:

1. Primary event only

With this option you will get a single row for each participant and will have access to all the core fields.
2. Subsequent events only

With this option, there are potentially multiple rows for each participant but there is no access to the primary event fields so it might not be possible to display the study ID, for example.
3. Primary and subsequent event mixture

The third option allows any combination for fields to be displayed and has multiple rows for each matching participant consisting of a header row that may include the study id, eligibility, consent etc. and subsequent rows that will not have those values but show follow-up event fields such as survey completion dates.

10.13 Live Filters (optional)

These are used to allow records to be filtered on screen *after* the report is generated. For example, your report may have a column that shows 'gender' this option could be used to Filter the display to only show "Male" or only show "Female" etc.

Step 4

This allows records to be sorted into the preferred sequence. This could perhaps be study ID, site or a particular event date such as randomisation date.

STEP 4

Order the Results (optional)

First by	record_id "Record ID" <input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="RBT"/>	Ascending order <input type="text"/>
Then by	Type variable name or field label <input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="RBT"/>	Ascending order <input type="text"/>
Then by	Type variable name or field label <input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="RBT"/>	Ascending order <input type="text"/>

[Cancel](#)

11. Alerts

Alerts have limitations. They do not work the same as Automated Survey Invites

REDCap alerts are triggered (or scheduled) as a reaction to a data change.

What this means is that the logic (which decides whether a REDCap alert will send for a record) can only scrutinize the data at the moment that the record is saved. It cannot scrutinize the data at an arbitrary later date when nothing has changed on the record.

This means that REDCap alerts cannot easily be used to alert to when something hasn't happened. For example, to send an email to a Study Team mailbox if a CRF hasn't been entered.

Where the alerts work well is to send an email alert when something has changed for a record in REDCap. Examples of where this might be useful is for example if a participant scores highly for something like suicide risk on a questionnaire. In this scenario REDCap can send an alert email to a Study Team mailbox to be actioned. Another example of where this might be used is if data is entered onto a Withdrawal or Death CRF, where a SAE check will need to be done.

12. File Repository

The File Repository allows users to store, organise and share files used in a REDCap project. Some files are auto-generated by the system (e.g. reports) and others can be uploaded, organised and shared with other project users. Folder access can be restricted by DAG and role.

Note: Files that are uploaded via the File Upload file type on an instrument (e.g. consent form, PIL, etc.) are NOT stored in the File Repository.

12.1 Navigating to the File Repository

The link to the File Repository can be found in the menu panel on the left-hand side.

This will open the screen File Repository.

File Repository

The File Repository allows users to store, organize, and share files used for this project. Folders and sub-folders can be created, and there is no limit to number of folders that can be created or the number of files that can be stored within them. If you are using Data Access Groups or user roles in the project, you may limit access to a new folder so that it is DAG-restricted and/or role-restricted. All deleted files will go to the Recycle Bin where they can be restored/undeleted for up to 30 days, after which they will be permanently deleted.

NOTE: Since Data Access Groups exist in this project, please be aware that any files uploaded here will be available to ALL project users unless the files have been uploaded into a DAG-restricted folder.

Drag and drop files here to upload

[Select files to upload](#)
[Create folder](#)
[Download](#)
[Delete](#)
[Move](#)

Show 25 entries

0.3 MB used

All Files

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Size	Time Uploaded	Comments	Share	Delete	doc_id / folder_id
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Data Export Files	1 Files					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miscellaneous File Attachments	0 Files					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recycle Bin	0 Files					
<input type="checkbox"/>	0028131785_20.jpg	309 KB	21-09-2023 13:54	Uploaded by tim.medicott.	Share	Delete	1358

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries Previous Next

12.2 Managing Your files

Files are stored in both system-generated folders and can also be organised in folders created by users.

System-generated folders

By default, there are three auto-generated folders available in your REDCap project.

Data Export Files

Whenever a data export is performed, the resulting files are also stored in the File Repository of the project. Their download is restricted to authorised users as set in the User Rights screen.

Miscellaneous File Attachments

Files stored here are added automatically by REDCap when users upload file attachments into text windows (e.g. when composing a survey invitation, adding a field label, or creating a project dashboard). Please be careful not to delete any files here unless you are absolutely sure that the file is no longer being used. **Deleting a file here that is used elsewhere in the project will cause the file's download link to no longer function and become a dead link.**

Recycle Bin

Deleted files are stored here for 30 days before they are permanently deleted.

Folders created by users

Users can create additional folders and sub-folders in their REDCap project.

Click the 'Create folder' button to create a new folder.

To add files to your project, click the 'Select files to upload' button or use the 'drag and drop' functionality. The file will then appear under 'All Files'.

If you would like to move a single file or a group of files to a new or existing folder, select the checkbox(es) next to the file name(s) or select the checkbox at the top to 'Select All'. Then you will be able to download, delete or move the selected file(s).

12.3 Restricting File Access

If you are using DAGs or user roles in your project, you can restrict access to folders so that their contents are only viewable by those users that have the right permissions. You can restrict folder access via the pop-up window **on creation** of a new folder.

Create folder
✕

You may create a new folder in the current directory. Once the folder has been created, you may navigate into it and upload files there.

New folder name:

Limit access by Data Access Group? (optional)
 Make folder accessible to

Limit access by User Role? (optional)
 Make folder accessible to

12.4 Recovering Deleted Files

All deleted files will be moved to the Recycle Bin. They can be restored for 30 days after which they will be permanently deleted.

All Files / Recycle Bin						
Name	Size	Time Uploaded	Comments	Time Deleted	Time until permanent deletion from Recycle Bin	Restore file

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

Previous 1 Next

To restore a file, you can use the green 'Restore file' button on the right-hand side.

13. REDCap Calendar

The Calendar application can be used to keep track of events or schedule assessments for your study/project within REDCap.

The benefits of using the REDCap calendar are:

- there is the option of associating each event with a record in REDCap,
- it can be synced with an external application
- it can be printed
- *Longitudinal data collection projects only: can produce schedules that are automatically generated from project-defined events such as visits or timepoints. Please note the data collection method will be set by the trial team and is not editable by sites. If you do not see the Scheduling module, this is not possible for your project*

13.1 Adding an Event to the Calendar (without linking to a record)

Navigate to the left-hand menu/Applications/select calendar:

The screenshot shows the REDCap Calendar interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with sections: 'My Projects', 'Project Home and Design', 'Data Collection', 'Applications' (where 'Calendar' is selected), and 'Help & Information'. The main area is titled 'Calendar' and includes a video link 'VIDEO: How to use the calendar (7 min)'. Below the title is a description: 'The Calendar application can be used as a project calendar within this project to help organize your schedule and keep track of any upcoming events. It will allow you to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format below. To add a new note or calendar event to any day, click +New at the top of that day's box to begin entering the information.' There are tabs for 'Day', 'Week', 'Month', and 'Agenda'. A 'Sync Calendar to External Application' button is on the right. Navigation arrows and dropdowns for 'October' and '2023' are present. A 'Print Calendar' button is also visible. The calendar grid shows days from Sunday to Saturday, with a '+ New' button in each cell. The date 18th is highlighted in yellow.

The calendar opens and different views can be selected as per the tabs at the top: Day/Week/Month.

You can navigate to the right day by using the arrow buttons on either side of the date above the calendar.

The Agenda function will only show events once they have been added to the Calendar.

Calendar [VIDEO: How to use the calendar \(7 min\)](#)

The Calendar application can be used as a project calendar within this project to help organize your schedule and keep track of any upcoming events. It will allow you to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format below. To add a new note or calendar event to any day, click **+New** at the top of that day's box to begin entering the information.

◀
October
▼
2023
▼
▶

Day	Time	Description
No calendar events to display		

To add a new event or note to any day/week/month (depending on view selected), click **+New** at the top of the respective day box.

w	16	+ New	17	+ New	18	+ New	19	+ New
w	23	+ New	24	+ New	25	+ New	26	+ New

A pop-up box appears to enter the new Event details.

Add New Calendar Event

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)**

Time: HH:MM (24-hr format)
(optional)

Notes:

Record ID: Select a record if the calendar event is associated with an existing record.

Time is an optional field.

Add New Calendar Event

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)**

Time: HH:MM (24-hr format)
(optional)

Notes:

Choose Time

Time **09:46**

Hour

Minute

Record ID: the calendar event is associated with an

Slider buttons can be used to set the time which displays in the 24 hour format, or the details can also be typed in. Once the correct Time displays, click Done or skip to the Notes box

Add New Calendar Event

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)**

Time: HH:MM (24-hr format)
(optional)

Notes:

Record ID: Select a record if the calendar event is associated with an existing record.

Enter any Notes in the Notes box. There is then the option to link to a Record ID.

If you don't want to associate the event with a Record, Click Add Calendar Event

✔Your new calendar event was created and added to the calendar!

A confirmation message will display confirming the event has been added.

Calendar [VIDEO: How to use the calendar \(7 min\)](#)

The Calendar application can be used as a project calendar within this project to help organize your schedule and keep track of any upcoming events. It will allow you to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format below. To add a new note or calendar event to any day, click **+New** at the top of that day's box to begin entering the information.

Day Week Month Agenda [Sync Calendar to External Application](#)

◀ October 2023 ▶ [Print Calendar](#)

Sunday	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
+ New 1	+ New 2	+ New 3	+ New 4	+ New 5	+ New 6	+ New 7
+ New 8	+ New 9	+ New 10	+ New 11	+ New 12	+ New 13	+ New 14
+ New 15	+ New 16	+ New 17	+ New 18 09:46 12 month as...	+ New 19	+ New 20	+ New 21
+ New 22	+ New 23	+ New 24	+ New 25	+ New 26	+ New 27	+ New 28
+ New 29	+ New 30	+ New 31				

The event will then show in the calendar.

13.2 Modifying or Editing a Saved Calendar Event

To change the details, click on the event from the Calendar

16	+ New	17	+ New	18	+ New	19	+ New	20	+ New
			09:46 12 mo	09:46 12 month assessment due					
23	+ New	24	+ New	25	+ New	26	+ New	27	+ New

The details will then display with the option to change date/time, edit notes and/or delete from calendar. The below example shows how to edit the time, but the same would apply for the date and notes.

View/Edit Calendar Event

Event Name: **Ad Hoc**

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)** [change date](#)

Time: **09:51** HH:MM

Notes:

Choose Time

Time **09:46**

Hour

Minute

Click on the time field, change and then click Done.

Click Save Time button

View/Edit Calendar Event

Event Name: **Ad Hoc**

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)** [change date](#)

Time: **09:41** [change time](#) **Saved!**

Notes:

'Saved!' will then show against the amended event detail. When editing Notes, if the text is amended but the Save Notes button is not clicked, REDCap will confirm 'Changes not saved'

View/Edit Calendar Event

Event Name: **Ad Hoc**

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)** [change date](#)

Time: **09:41** [change time](#)

Notes:

Changes not saved

Once the details are corrected, click on Close in the top-right

View/Edit Calendar Event

Event Name: **Ad Hoc**

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)** [change date](#)

Time: **09:41** [change time](#)

Notes:

✔ Saved!

13.3 Deleting a Calendar Event

To delete the event, click back into the event and click on the 'Delete from Calendar' button in the bottom right

REDCap will display a warning message. If you want to proceed, click Ok. If you wish to retain the event, click Cancel

Your calendar event was successfully deleted!

A confirmation message will display when the event has been deleted and it will no longer show in the calendar

Calendar

[VIDEO: How to use the calendar \(7 min\)](#)

The Calendar application can be used as a project calendar within this project to help organize your schedule and keep track of any upcoming events. It will allow you to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format below. To add a new note or calendar event to any day, click **+New** at the top of that day's box to begin entering the information.

Day Week Month Agenda [Sync Calendar to External Application](#)

October 2023 [Print Calendar](#)

Sunday	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
+ New 1	+ New 2	+ New 3	+ New 4	+ New 5	+ New 6	+ New 7
+ New 8	+ New 9	+ New 10	+ New 11	+ New 12	+ New 13	+ New 14
+ New 15	+ New 16	+ New 17	+ New 18	+ New 19	+ New 20	+ New 21
+ New 22	+ New 23	+ New 24	+ New 25	+ New 26	+ New 27	+ New 28

13.4 Linking an Event to a Record

Either create a new calendar event as per section 1.1 or edit an existing event as per section 1.3. Go to the last box, Record ID and click on the drop-down option.

Add New Calendar Event

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)**

Time: HH:MM (24-hr format)
(optional)

Notes:

Record ID: Select a record if the calendar event is associated with an existing record.

Select the Record ID you wish to link to.

Add New Calendar Event

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)**

Time: HH:MM (24-hr format)
(optional)

Notes:

Record ID: Select a record if the calendar event is associated with an existing record.

Click Add calendar event button. The confirmation message will display to confirm it has been added. The event will now display in all views including the Agenda view which will list events.

Calendar

[VIDEO: How to use the calendar \(7 min\)](#)

The Calendar application can be used as a project calendar within this project to help organize your schedule and keep track of any upcoming events. It will allow you to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format below. To add a new note or calendar event to any day, click **+New** at the top of that day's box to begin entering the information.

Day Week Month Agenda [Sync Calendar to External Application](#)

◀
October
▼
2023
▼
▶
[Print Calendar](#)

Day	Time	Description
Wed Oct 18	09:03	1 - call XXX

No details can be edited from the Agenda view. You must navigate back to Day/Week/Month view to edit or delete.

Once saved, the event will show on the Project Home page

Project Statistics	
Records in project	4
Most recent activity	18-10-2023 12:14
Space usage for docs	1.13 MB

Upcoming Calendar Events (next 7 days)		
Time	Date	Description
09:03	18-10-2023	1 - call XXX

By clicking on the magnifying glass, you can view/edit the event from this page.

... (if any).

Project Statistics	
Records in project	4
Most recent activity	18-10-2023 12:14
Space usage for docs	1.13 MB

Upcoming Calendar Events (next 7 days)		
Time	Date	Description
09:03	18-10-2023	1 - call XXX

From this view, you can go directly to the Record by clicking on 'View Record Home Page'

View/Edit Calendar Event

Record ID: **1** [View Record Home Page](#)

Event Name: Ad Hoc

Date: **18-10-2023 (Wednesday)** [change date](#)

Time: **09:03** [change time](#)

Notes:

This enables you to quickly go to the Associated Record for data entry.

Record Home Page

The grid below displays the form-by-form progress of data entered for the currently selected record. You may click on the colored status icons to access that form/event.

Choose action for record

Legend for status icons:

- Incomplete Incomplete (no data saved) ?
- Unverified Partial Survey Response
- Complete Completed Survey Response

Record ID 1 1 upcoming calendar event

Data Collection Instrument	Screening	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Patient Details (survey)	●			
Screening Log	●			
Randomisation	○			
Treatment		○	○	○
Questionnaire (survey)	●			
Withdrawal	○			
Note to File	○			

Equally, you can also view the Calendar event from within the Record by clicking on the '1 upcoming calendar event' button above the table. Note this shows events coming up for the next 7 days only

Instrument	Screening	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
	●			
	●			
	○			
	●			
	○			
	○			

Upcoming Calendar Events

The table below displays this record's upcoming calendar events for the next 7 days.

Time	Date	Description
🔍 09:03	18-10-2023	1 - call XXX

To edit or view click on the magnifying glass or click Close.

13.5 Syncing to an External Calendar

To sync the events to an external calendar, click on 'Sync Calendar to External Application' button on the top right of the calendar display

Calendar [VIDEO: How to use the calendar \(7 min\)](#)

The Calendar application can be used as a project calendar within this project to help organize your schedule and keep track of any upcoming events. It will allow you to add or modify calendar events and then view them either in a daily, weekly, or monthly format below. To add a new note or calendar event to any day, click **+New** at the top of that day's box to begin entering the information.

Day Week Month Agenda

◀
October
▼
2023
▶

Sunday	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
+ New 1	+ New 2	+ New 3	+ New 4	+ New 5	+ New 6	+ New 7
+ New 8	+ New 9	+ New 10	+ New 11	+ New 12	+ New 13	+ New 14

Instructions will then display to link to an external calendar.

Follow these steps to link to external calendars that support iCal or ICS files either online or offline.

13.6 Longitudinal Designs

If your research project includes more than one visit and the Scheduling module is enabled, you can configure your study's events grid so that events are automatically added to the calendar for any new record ID's or for remaining events on existing records.

If this feature is enabled, a 'Scheduling' section will appear under 'Data Collection' in the left-hand navigation menu.

13.7 Define Events

First you need to define your study events. Certain permissions need to be granted to enable you to do this.

From the left-hand navigation, under Data Collection, click on 'Scheduling'. This brings up instructions on how to generate a new schedule: 'Create Schedule' or 'View or Edit Schedule' as per the two tabs.

From the 'Create Schedule' section, click on the 'Define my Events' link listed in the instructions. If an error message displays stating you do not have access, please contact your project administrator to query your access rights. You will not be able to use this function otherwise. If you are able to use this function, further instructions will display to create events

Under the instructions, there is a basic example of an event grid. To add new events, enter the days offset (how many days after the initial event, the event should happen), offset range, event label and if required a custom event label; this is used to link to the variable in the database. If your project has different Arms, each Arm can be added and will appear as separate tabs in the table (first tab is Arm 1, second tab is Add New Arm). In this example, 'phone call' has been added.

13.8 Linking Events to Data Instruments

Once you have created your Events, the instruments need to be assigned to the event which can be accessed via the link in step #2 or from the tabs at the top of the page. Further instructions display. The below screenshot shows a few saved instruments; the green tick indicates the events are saved against the Data Instrument. 'The created event 'phone call' is currently not linked to any Data Instruments

[VIDEO](#)

Project Setup Define My Events Designate Instruments for My Events

Since you have defined multiple events on the [Define My Events](#) page, you may now select which data collection instruments to utilize for each event by using the table below. This allows you to enter data on any data collection form for any project record. Any and all data collection instruments can thus be used for any event defined.

Click the *Begin Editing* button to change the relationships below by designating which forms you wish to use. Once you are finished making changes, click the *Save* button to finalize your changes.

Upload or c

Begin Editing Save

Data Collection Instrument	Screening (1)	Treatment 1 (2)	Treatment 2 (3)	phone call (4)	Treatment 3 (5)
Patient Details (survey)	✓				
Screening Log	✓				
Randomisation	✓				
Treatment		✓	✓		✓
Questionnaire (survey)	✓				
Withdrawal	✓				
Note to File	✓				

To add events to data instruments, click on *Begin Editing*. In editing mode, the boxes will change to grey. Tick to select or Untick to remove the event against the required Data Instrument. Click *Save* once finished; the events table will display the green ticks to show it's saved. 'Phone call' is now linked to 'Treatment' and 'Withdrawal'

Begin Editing Save Select All Deselect All

Data Collection Instrument	Screening (1)	Treatment 1 (2)	Treatment 2 (3)	phone call (4)	Treatment 3 (5)
Patient Details (survey)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Screening Log	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Randomisation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Treatment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Questionnaire (survey)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Withdrawal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Note to File	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

From the left-hand navigation, go to Data Collection and click on Record Status Dashboard. The event will display linked to the data instruments e.g. phone call shows against data instrument Treatment and Withdrawal

+ Add new record

Displaying: Instrument status only | [Lock status only](#) | [All status types](#)

Record ID	Screening						Treatment 1	Treatment 2	phone call		Treatment 3
	Patient Details	Screening Log	Randomisation	Questionnaire	Withdrawal	Note to File	Treatment	Treatment	Treatment	Withdrawal	Treatment
1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
3	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
824-1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●

13.9 Creating a Schedule of Events Linked to Data Instruments

To create the schedule, click on Data Collection/Scheduling: Add a new record ID or choose an existing record. Click on the 'Generate Schedule' button.

Projected Schedule for "4" (NOTE: The dates below have NOT yet been scheduled.)

The projected schedule below was automatically generated for **Record ID "4"** based on your pre-defined Events. You may change the value of any dates generated below simply by clicking inside the date box and selecting a new date. Any dates generated below that fall on weekends will be listed in red. Click the *Create Schedule* button to finalize this schedule, which will then be added to the Calendar.

Time (optional)	Date / Day of Week	Event Name
<input type="checkbox"/>	10-11-2023 Friday Range: 09-11-2023 - 11-11-2023	phone call
<input type="checkbox"/>	11-11-2023 Saturday	Screening
<input type="checkbox"/>	12-11-2023 Sunday	Treatment 1
<input type="checkbox"/>	13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 2
<input type="checkbox"/>	14-11-2023 Tuesday	Treatment 3

NOTE: Clicking the *Create Schedule* button will additionally add "4" as a new Record ID.

Days on weekends are listed in red for ease of finding and changing. Click in the Time box to add a time, or in the Date / Day of Week to edit.

Projected Schedule for "4" (NOTE: The dates below have NOT yet been scheduled.)

The projected schedule below was automatically generated for **Record ID "4"** based on your pre-defined Events. You may change the value of any dates generated below simply by clicking inside the date box and selecting a new date. Any dates generated below that fall on weekends will be listed in red. Click the *Create Schedule* button to finalize this schedule, which will then be added to the Calendar.

Time (optional)	Date / Day of Week	Event Name
<input type="checkbox"/>	10-11-2023 Friday Range: 09-11-2023 - 11-11-2023	phone call
<input type="checkbox"/>	13-11-2023 Monday	Screening
<input type="checkbox"/>	13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 1
<input type="checkbox"/>	13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 2
<input type="checkbox"/>	14-11-2023 Tuesday	Treatment 3

NOTE: Clicking the *Create Schedule* button will additionally add "4" as a new Record ID.

Click on Create schedule.

✔ Successfully Scheduled "4"

Record ID "4" was successfully scheduled for the dates and times below and has been added to the [Calendar](#). You may now edit this schedule or add more information, such as changing the status (e.g., 'Cancelled', 'Confirmed') or adding descriptive notes, by clicking the [View](#) or [Edit Schedule](#) tab above.

Schedule for "4"		
Time	Date	Event Name
	10-11-2023 Friday	phone call
	13-11-2023 Monday	Screening
	13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 1
	13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 2
	14-11-2023 Tuesday	Treatment 3

From the left-hand navigation: Applications/Calendar, the scheduled events will now display. Double click on the events to open the pop-up box which will display the details: Record ID, event name, status, scheduled due date

Sunday	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
			+ New 1	+ New 2	+ New 3	+ New 4
+ New 5	+ New 6	+ New 7	+ New 8	+ New 9	+ New 10 ☆ 4 (phone call)	+ New 11
+ New 12	+ New 13 ☆ 4 (Screening) ☆ 4 (Treatment 1) ☆ 4 (Treatment 2)	+ New 14 ☆ 4 (Treatment 3)	+ New 15	+ New 16	+ New 17	+ New 18
+ New 19	+ New 20	+ New 21	+ New 22	+ New 23	+ New 24	+ New 25
+ New 26	+ New 27	+ New 28	+ New 29	+ New 30		

From the pop-up box, you can navigate to 'View schedule' or 'View Record Home page' by clicking on the links next to the Record ID or navigate directly to the Data Entry forms by clicking on the buttons listed on the right.

Close

View/Edit Calendar Event

Record ID: **4** [View Schedule](#) [View Record Home Page](#)

Event Name: **phone call**

Status: ☆ **Due Date** [change status](#)

Date: **10-11-2023 (Friday)**

Time: HH:MM

Notes:

Data Entry Forms

Treatment

Withdrawal

13.10 Editing or Deleting a Schedule

To edit the Schedule, click on 'Scheduling' and the 'View or Edit Schedule' tab.

Scheduling

 [VIDEO: How to use the](#)

To view or edit the calendar events of a previously scheduled Record ID, select it from the drop-down menu below.

Select a previously scheduled Record ID:

View/Edit Existing Schedule for "4"

Below are the calendar events for **Record ID "4"**. Dates that fall on weekends will be listed in **red**. You may edit any calendar event by clicking the View icon. You may also add a new unscheduled event at the bottom of the table by selecting a date and clicking the **Add** button.

	Time	Date / Day of Week <small>D-M-Y</small>	Event Name	Status	Notes
		10-11-2023 Friday <small>Range: 09-11-2023 - 11-11-2023</small>	phone call	☆ Due Date	
		13-11-2023 Monday	Screening	☆ Due Date	
		13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 1	☆ Due Date	
		13-11-2023 Monday	Treatment 2	☆ Due Date	
		14-11-2023 Tuesday	Treatment 3	☆ Due Date	

 Add new Ad Hoc calendar event on

 [Print Schedule](#)

Click on the pencil to edit or red cross to delete. You can also print the schedule from here or add a new event.

13.11 Viewing the Schedule from the Record Status Dashboard

From the Record Status Dashboard, a button will appear next to the Record ID '5 upcoming calendar events'.

Record Home Page

The grid below displays the form-by-form progress of data entered for the currently selected record. You may click on the colored status icons to access that form/event. If you wish, you may modify the events below by navigating to the [Define My Events](#) page.

Legend for status icons:

- Incomplete
- Incomplete (no data saved) ?
- Unverified
- Partial Survey Response
- Complete
- Completed Survey Response

[Choose action for record](#)

Record ID 4 successfully edited.

Record ID 4

5 upcoming calendar events

Data Collection Instrument	phone call	Screening	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Patient Details (survey)		●			
Screening Log		●			
Randomisation		●			
Treatment	●		●	●	●
Questionnaire (survey)		●			
Withdrawal	●	●			
Note to File		●			
Delete all data on event:	✗				

Click on the button to see the events due.

Record Home Page

The grid below displays the form-by-form progress of data entered for the currently selected record. You may click on the colored status icons to access that form/event. If you wish, you may modify the events below by navigating to the [Define My Events](#) page.

Legend for status icons:

- Incomplete ● Incomplete (no data saved) ?
- Unverified ● Partial Survey Response
- Complete ✔ Completed Survey Response

Upcoming Calendar Events

The table below displays this record's upcoming calendar events for the next 7 days.

Time	Date	Description
	10-11-2023	4 (phone call)
	13-11-2023	4 (Screening)
	13-11-2023	4 (Treatment 1)
	13-11-2023	4 (Treatment 2)
	14-11-2023	4 (Treatment 3)

Once an event has been marked as Complete or Incomplete, the event will change to Green or Red on the Record Home page and on the Record Status Dashboard.

Record Status Dashboard (all records)

Displayed below is a table listing all existing records/responses and their status for every data collection instrument (and if longitudinal, for every event). You may click any of the colored buttons in the table to open a new tab/window in your browser to view that record on that particular data collection instrument. Please note that if your form-level user privileges are restricted for certain data collection instruments, you will only be able to view those instruments, and if you belong to a Data Access Group, you will only be able to view records that belong to your group.

Legend for status icons:

- Incomplete ● Incomplete (no data saved) ?
- Unverified ● Partial Survey Response
- Complete ✔ Completed Survey Response

Dashboard displayed: [Default dashboard] Create custom dashboard

Displaying Data Access Group: -- ALL --

Displaying record: Page 1 of 1: "1" through "824-1" of 5 records ALL (5) records per page

+ Add new record

Displaying: [Instrument status only](#) | [Lock status only](#) | [All status types](#)

Record ID	phone call		Screening					Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3	
	Treatment	Withdrawal	Patient Details	Screening Log	Randomisation	Questionnaire	Withdrawal	Note to File	Treatment	Treatment	Treatment
1											
2											
3											
4											
824-1											